

Deliverable D1.21

9th GDI quarterly implementation report

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Table of contents

Contents

1. Executive Summary	3
2. Contribution towards project outcomes	5
3. Methods	7
4. Description of work accomplished	7
4.1 Monitoring of the technical expertise deployment - Q9 results	7
4.1.1 Deployment of technical expertise at the GDI Node Level - Q9	7
4.2 Monitoring the evolution of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure Nodes - Q9 results	9
4.2.1 GDI Node Operational Readiness level - Q9 results	9
4.2.2. GDI Node general progress indicator - Q9 results	11
4.2.3. GDI Node general progress indicator - Capacity building actions	14
5. Results	15
6. Discussion	16
7. Conclusions & Impact	16
8. Next steps	16
Annex I. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Onboarding Summary	17
Annex II. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Onboarding	18
Annex III. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Deployment	19
Annex IV. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Operational	20
Annex V. Timelines for implementation according to target phase as	21
Annex VI. Visual progress of the Node Advancement	23

1. Executive Summary

The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) is a deployment project co-funded by the Digital Europe programme. GDI's main objective is to realise the data infrastructure required by the 1+MG initiative to share high-quality genotypic and phenotypic data across borders, the 1+MG Virtual Cohort. Countries participating have committed to reach a concrete operational level before the end of the project (progressing across different phases: onboarding, deployment or operational), which will require them to fulfil technical and non-technical requirements.

In addition, the establishment of required technical capacity in each Node has been identified as a critical factor for the success of the project and the long-term sustainability of the data infrastructure and the initiative.

This document presents the results of the initial European Genomic Data Infrastructure monitoring activities laid out in D1.12¹ that are initially focussed on:

- **the deployment of the technical expertise** required to deploy and operate the European Genomic Data Infrastructure to share access to data across borders, building the technical capacity to run the infrastructure beyond the end of the project, and,
- **the evolution of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure Nodes.** GDI Nodes will transition across different phases in their journey to be fully operational and integrated into the European Genomic Data Infrastructure.
- **identifying capacity-building actions required to target onboarding.** We acknowledge the different access to skills and resources each GDI Node has which implies that GDI Nodes will evolve and reach operational readiness at different speeds. We will use the information collected from GDI Nodes to identify gaps and opportunities to build capacity across the nodes both at the technical level and not technical levels to accelerate the journey across the different phases. In this case, we will focus on the onboarding phase.

These monitoring processes and tools aim to support GDI Nodes in their journey by assessing their progress on a quarterly basis and providing them with useful guidance and recommendations to reach their individual and project objectives, summarised in the commitment to have **6 Nodes technically operational by 2024**. This will be extended to **15 Nodes by 2026** with three additional Nodes reaching deployment and six more Nodes reaching onboarding.

A summary of the information collected every quarter will be presented to the 1+MG Group (in addition to being shared with project participants) in order to gather the contributions and support of the 1+MG Group on the direction of travel and their assistance in removing any roadblocks that could be identified.

The information presented here corresponds to the status of the Nodes by M30.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7576210#.ZEYoBuzMJqs>

The current scope and content of the quarterly report could be updated if there is a need to modify it to better support the countries in their commitments or to facilitate reaching the overall project's initiatives. For instance, monitoring of the volume of data available in the European Genome Dashboard or via the 1+MG infrastructure could be implemented in the near future.

B1MG² has released the first full version of the 1+MG Framework³, which is a useful resource to build capacity and facilitate the dissemination of the 1+MG recommendation and guidelines coming from the project support the implementation (B1MG, GDI, GoE, EHDS,...). The first official release in November 2023 is comprised mainly of B1MG outputs, but this alone could help GDI members to navigate recommendations and understand how the different components work together and align with the EHDS. The framework will now be updated and maintained by GDI, thus incorporating the latest resources that support the vision of the 1+MG initiative.

² <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

³ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

Outcomes	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi-party authorisation and authentication system, and enable the application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	No

<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable the extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

The methods and processes to gather the monitoring information were established in D1.12⁴. In this report, we will present and analyse the data initially collected as part of the periodic reporting exercise.

4. Description of work accomplished

Project participants and GDI Nodes were asked to provide the monitoring information related to the deployment of the technical expertise and the self-evaluation of the Node status.

4.1 Monitoring of the technical expertise deployment - Q9 results

4.1.1 Deployment of technical expertise at the GDI Node Level - Q9

The data show that **71.8%** of the expected technical expertise to be in place on average during the duration of the project was deployed, however 20.6% of institutes did not report their FTE usage this quarter. All countries have started to use their allocated FTEs with particular countries (such as Belgium, Spain, Cyprus, Malta, and Romania) that may need targeted support. However, this is a marked improvement over past quarters, indicating that national capacity is improving.

Project participants have reported delays in recruitment and some of them are also reorganising the national activities, which is expected to still have an effect in the forthcoming reports while the technical experts get fully deployed across all GDI Nodes. Some Nodes have managed to progress their work in concert with other projects, thus had not been claiming against their GDI FTE usage. It is possible that these grants have ended, and thus FTE usage has increased.

The continued development across all of the three pillars will support the Nodes in guiding on how best to deploy their technical expertise. However, further development in this area is still required. The coordination team met in August, 2024 to come up with a plan to support technical expertise deployment at the Nodes. Over the coming months, they will send the Nodes a survey on current and planned FTE usage for Node and project development and will follow up with 1:1 conversations, starting with the Operational goal Nodes and moving down from there. The Q1 2025 requirements freezing activities have also helped pinpoint where development is required and WP3 can guide these Nodes towards adding technical expertise in these areas. Additionally, other opportunities exist to leverage the existing funding for project support, including:

- Support additional countries in joining GDI
- Using Operational-goal Node project support FTEs to "mentor" Deployment & Onboarding Nodes
- Increase involvement of Nodes in WP6 to build data management capacity across all Nodes to accelerate the flow of data in compliance with the 1+MG Framework

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7576210#.ZEYoBuzMJqs>

- Guidelines/processes to prepare primary use data for secondary use, data quality aspects
- Federated/Distributed analytics Governance

Table 1 Deployment of technical expertise across GDI Nodes

GDI Node	Operational Readiness (target)	Technical expertise deployment Pillar II		Based on inputs from 79.4%
		Baseline FTEs	Actuals FTEs	Actuals / Baseline
Belgium	Operational	4.0	1.0	24%
Czech Republic	Operational	4.0	2.8	71%
Denmark	Operational	4.0	1.8	44%
Estonia	Operational	4.0	4.7	118%
Finland	Operational	4.0	5.6	141%
France	Operational	3.4	3.5	101%
Germany	Operational	4.0	1.5	38%
Italy	Operational	3.9	1.8	46%
Luxembourg	Operational	4.3	3.7	88%
Portugal	Operational	4.0	4.3	107%
Slovenia	Operational	4.0	1.9	47%
Spain	Operational	5.0	1.2	24%
Sweden	Operational	5.0	4.1	83%
The Netherlands	Operational	5.0	4.6	91%
Norway	Operational	4.0	1.7	43%
Bulgaria	Deployment	1.8	2.0	113%
Latvia	Deployment	2.0	1.7	85%
Lithuania	Deployment	2.0	2.0	100%
Croatia	Onboarding	1.0	0.9	90%
Ireland	Onboarding	1.2	0.7	60%
Cyprus	Onboarding	0.9	0.2	18%
Hungary	Onboarding	0.9	0.4	48%

Malta	Onboarding	0.0	0.0	0%
Romania	Onboarding	0.5	0.1	22%
Total:		72.8	52.3	71.8%

4.2 Monitoring the evolution of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure Nodes - Q9 results

- The main purpose of the GDI Nodes Operational Readiness data gathering is to monitor the Nodes' journey and identify capacity-building actions that will help them meet their targets by the end of the project.
- The Nodes have defined their timeline for advancement along the defined path towards operational readiness as illustrated in D3.2. However, this deliverable received limited input from the Nodes. Indicative timelines have been established for countries that have not provided a new roadmap based on the original data given at the onset of the project. As technical deployment has proceeded, we have begun to receive requests to update the timelines to match the technical and administrative realities the Nodes are facing. Countries have been encouraged to update their timelines based on recent developments. During the March 2024 meeting, Nodes timelines for the fulfilment of the commitments established in the 1+MG Roadmap⁵ and the project was presented ([see annexe V](#)) as well as recommended actions to demonstrate the development of technical capacity, the coordinator will follow up with the Nodes to ensure follow-through.
- There are two different views provided from the collected data, detailed in the following sections: 4.2.1: The level of operational readiness and 4.2.2: the overall percentage of progress across all indicators.
- Further analysis of the overall progress has been provided to identify capacity-building and other actions required to support nodes to reach the onboarding stage and beyond, as indicated by the Node roadmap.

4.2.1 GDI Node Operational Readiness level - Q9 results

- The GDI Node Operational Readiness level shows the expected phase Nodes should have attained by the time that the data is collected: Onboarding, Deployment and Operational, and where the GDI Nodes see themselves (self-evaluation) at the time of providing the information.

⁵<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/1million-genomes-initiative-new-roadmap-adopted-scale-and-sustainability-phase>

- The Q9 progress was focused on finalising the requirements for GDI, analysing the gaps, and assigning the responsible parties, which will continue into the next quarter. This development will help guide Node advancement as well as providing them with solid specifications to support their own technical and financial planning.
- At this point, 2 Nodes (Spain and Sweden) have attained the full Onboarding level. Slovenia has joined Norway, Finland and Portugal in meeting all of the technical indicators for Onboarding, with 6 Nodes now reaching that level.
- Italy, Lithuania, Spain, France, Ireland and Sweden are still the only Nodes completing all of the non-technical indicators (see Annexe I).
- 12 of the 15 Operational-goal Nodes have reported that they have now completed 80% or more of the combined technical and non-technical steps required to reach Onboarding, bringing them into a position to complete the steps in the next two quarters. The Nodes that have not (Czech Republic, Luxembourg and The Netherlands) will be approached by WP5 to see what additional support is required. However, the Netherlands and the Czech Republic have both made progress since last quarter.
- One of the technical indicators that many countries have not completed is 1.6.1, "Have deployed and validated an instance or PoC or an upgraded version incorporating additional use cases". As MS8 is focused on incorporation of a use case, we would expect many more Nodes to complete this shortly, now that the milestone has been completed. Another barrier that remains is the resistance of some Nodes to deploying software that has not yet reached production-readiness. Coordination is working with these Nodes to view the attainment of production-ready software as a collective goal of the Operational Nodes.
- 95% of the Nodes filled in the quarterly monitoring form this quarter, so the current numbers give a relatively clear picture of the current state of the Nodes.

Table 2 GDI Nodes Operational Readiness level by M30

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GDI Node Operational Readiness	Start date Duration By Month	2022-11		Overall status:	
		48			
		30	2025-4		
Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Vanguard Node?	Expected Phase	Current Phase	Technical Phase
Operational	Belgium	Yes	Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Czech Republic		Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Denmark		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Operational	Estonia		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Operational	Finland	Yes	Operational	TBD	Onboarding
Operational	France		Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Germany		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Operational	Italy		Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Luxembourg	Yes	Operational	TBD	TBD
Operational	Portugal		Deployment	TBD	Onboarding
Operational	Slovenia		Onboarding	TBD	Onboarding
Operational	Spain	Yes	Deployment	Onboarding	Onboarding
Operational	Sweden	Yes	Deployment	Onboarding	Onboarding
Operational	The Netherlands	Yes	Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Norway	Yes	Onboarding	TBD	Onboarding
Deployment	Bulgaria		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Deployment	Latvia		TBD	TBD	TBD
Deployment	Lithuania		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Croatia		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Ireland		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Cyprus		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Hungary		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Malta		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Romania		TBD	TBD	TBD

Note: The “Expected Phase” is based on the Node Roadmap provided in D3.2. For the countries that have not given an updated timeline, the default timeline provided during the planning phase has been used.

4.2.2. GDI Node general progress indicator - Q9 results

The GDI Node general progress indicator view, provides us with a metric that looks at all the individual steps across all the phases of the GDI Node Operational Readiness and calculates an

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indicator of progress (%) based on how each individual question, regardless of its level, has been answered, assigning a score as follows:

- 1.0 if the step has been met,
- 0.5 if the step has been met partially or,
- 0.0 if not met or not reported

Table 3 GDI Node general progress indicator and comparison with previous quarter data

M30-Q9								
M30 Reporting Complete	GDI Node Operational Readiness	Step Phase Type						
	Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Vanguard Node	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes =1, Partially =0.5)	Previous Quarter	Change since previous quarter
yes	Operational	Belgium	Deployment	Yes	TBD	32%	32%	0%
yes	Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment		TBD	29%	29%	0%
yes	Operational	Denmark	Onboarding		TBD	53%	53%	0%
yes	Operational	Estonia	Onboarding		TBD	35%	35%	0%
yes	Operational	Finland	Operational	Yes	TBD	47%	47%	0%
yes	Operational	France	Deployment		TBD	53%	49%	4%
yes	Operational	Germany	Onboarding		TBD	49%	46%	3%
yes	Operational	Italy	Deployment		TBD	40%	40%	0%
yes	Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	Yes	TBD	25%	25%	0%
yes	Operational	Portugal	Deployment		TBD	50%	50%	0%
yes	Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding		TBD	49%	46%	3%
yes	Operational	Spain	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	49%	49%	0%
no	Operational	Sweden	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	51%	51%	0%
yes	Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	Yes	TBD	38%	32%	6%
yes	Operational	Norway	Onboarding	Yes	TBD	43%	40%	3%
yes	Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding		TBD	22%	19%	3%
yes	Deployment	Latvia	TBD		TBD	22%	21%	1%
yes	Deployment	Lithuania	TBD		TBD	32%	31%	1%
yes	Onboarding	Croatia	TBD		TBD	13%	13%	0%
yes	Onboarding	Ireland	TBD		TBD	19%	19%	0%
yes	Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD		TBD	12%	7%	4%
no	Onboarding	Hungary	TBD		TBD	25%	25%	0%
yes	Onboarding	Malta	TBD		TBD	15%	12%	3%
yes	Onboarding	Romania	TBD		TBD	9%	7%	1%
95%						33.82%		1%

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For a breakdown of progress within the Onboarding indicators, see Annexe I. Progress within the Operational-goal Nodes has been particularly slow this quarter, however many of the developers have been focused on completing the European-level. The requirements setting activities that are ongoing now will be another major boost in the coming quarters. Many Nodes have expressed that it is difficult to convince their management to deploy software before all of the requirements have been finalised, so these requirements-setting actions should support deployment for Nodes with these challenges. Finally, hiring remains a challenge, particularly for Deployment and Onboarding-goal Nodes, and, well-aligned with the levels of technical expertise deployment seen in Table 1, several countries have noted that further advancements can be made once local experts have been hired and this activity remains ongoing.

4.2.3. GDI Node general progress indicator - Capacity building actions

At this point in the project, seven Nodes have planned to achieve a stage beyond Onboarding, however most Nodes are still working through the Onboarding indicators, so support for advancement is focussed on these indicators. That said, there has been improvement since last quarter, particularly in the Deployment indicators in the Operational-goal Nodes since last quarter. In the “Onboarding” section, all indicators are at greater than 50% overall completion. Because of this, the indicators examined below focus on those below 90% completion by Operational-goal Nodes with the idea that these Nodes can guide the less mature Nodes in the coming year. Looking at the information provided by the Nodes, clear actions emerge to build capacity both across Technical and non-technical requirements (see [Annexe II](#)). For the calculation, a “yes” answer is considered 100% complete, a “no” is 0% and “partially” is 50% for each country:

- Onboarding steps with **0-50% completion** across **Operational-goal Nodes**
 - **N/A**
- Onboarding steps with **51-75% completion** across **Operational-goal Nodes**
 - **Have developed a national genomic plan or similar that secures long-term funding that matches the target implementation level.**
 - **Action:** A workshop took place coordinated by ISCIII about the successful strategies of countries who have put a national genomic plan in place. The outputs and videos from this event will be shared on the Framework and will be linked to from the operational readiness reporting spreadsheet. Furthermore, there is extensive planning underway to support Node development in this area, coordinated by ISCIII.
- Onboarding steps with **76-90% completion** across **Operational-goal Nodes**
 - **API use cases considered, specifications drafted and implementation in progress**
 - **Action:** Some countries are still recruiting technical developers, but most that have not completed this step are working on applying the GDI use cases to national contexts. MS8 has a focus on ensuring that the APIs meet use case

requirements, so this should assist most Nodes in completing this indicator. As for country-specific needs, the Nodes are in a state where they are drafting their use cases and what will be required to meet them, with some Nodes working on hiring someone to manage this.

- **Decision on services and components utilised**
 - While all Operational-goal Nodes have begun this, some Nodes have identified challenges in finalising their services and components. These include waiting on fully defined APIs and protocols, seeking long-term commitment on some technical components (ie. federated analysis, etc), as well as challenges on waiting for internal national decisions to be made that will impact national infrastructure decisions. The finalisation of the requirements, which is now completed, should support the challenges with a project dependency.
- **Security mitigation, management, and reporting system being drafted.**
 - **Action:** Most Nodes indicate that this work is underway and the information they require is available. A FitSM workshop was held this quarter to help guide Nodes in this process. We expect to see progress in the next two quarters.
- **Have deployed and validated an instance or PoC or an upgraded version incorporating additional use cases**
 - **Action:** The detailed explanation of this indicator requires that the proof of concept has been implemented and tested. Nodes involved in MS7 and 8 have done well here, but the other Nodes are lagging. The completion of MS8, which incorporates a use case into the infrastructure demonstrator, should provide the Nodes what they need to complete this milestone, but an internal deadline might be required.
- Deployment steps
 - Many of the Nodes should have made significant progress in these by this point. While there are still gaps that remain for the Operational-goal Nodes within Onboarding, coordination and WP3 needs to generally pressure and support Nodes into making progress into further steps. National capacity and upgrading the infrastructure to meet operational needs seem to be key gaps in this area.

5. Results

- Use of resources has improved markedly this quarter. However, there are still a number of Operational-goal Nodes who need to be contributing towards the European level infrastructure. WP3, with the support of Coordination, will be addressing this in the coming quarter.
- Within the Nodes that were expected to have already reached the Onboarding stage, the two most commonly incomplete indicators are the PoC run with a use case and the completion of a National Genomic Plan. The work for MS8 is focused on this work and completion will help Nodes meet this indicator as well as the freezing of the proposed minimum required feature set for the scope of the GDI project. The recent national genomic plan workshop should help

with the latter, but it is ultimately up to the governments to meet this requirement. We will keep monitoring the indicators and reinforce the support during the planned Pillar II meetings.

- Additional capacity-building actions have been identified.

6. Discussion

The lack of a defined final feature set had been a major hurdle for deployment. Now that this has been set and the information is available to all within the project, the coordination team believes that the Nodes will be able to make significant progress in the coming months. Emphasising the plan for 6 continuous months of operation before the end of the project may be required to push the Nodes into completing their technical deployment steps.

7. Conclusions & Impact

Use of resources has improved, but it has not come with seeing contribution to the European-level infrastructure from some key Operational-goal Nodes. WP4 is working with Coordination to push these Nodes into action.

Identified technical capacity-building actions (section [4.2.3](#)) have been outlined, but a concrete plan needs to be put in place to support these when MS8 development work is completed.

8. Next steps

The next gathering of information from Nodes will take place in August, 2025.

Annex I. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Onboarding Summary

Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node					Step Phase Type			
	Expected Phase	Vanguard Node	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes =1, Partially =0.5)	Onboarding Overall Progress	Onboarding Tech Progress	Onboarding NonTech Progress		
Operational	Belgium	Deployment	Yes	TBD	32%	85%	86%	83%	
Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment		TBD	29%	70%	64%	83%	
Operational	Denmark	Onboarding		TBD	53%	90%	93%	83%	
Operational	Estonia	Onboarding		TBD	35%	80%	93%	50%	
Operational	Finland	Operational	Yes	TBD	47%	95%	100%	83%	
Operational	France	Deployment		TBD	53%	95%	93%	100%	
Operational	Germany	Onboarding		TBD	49%	90%	93%	83%	
Operational	Italy	Deployment		TBD	40%	90%	86%	100%	
Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	Yes	TBD	25%	70%	64%	83%	
Operational	Portugal	Deployment		TBD	50%	90%	100%	67%	
Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding		TBD	49%	95%	100%	83%	
Operational	Spain	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	49%	100%	100%	100%	
Operational	Sweden	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	51%	100%	100%	100%	
Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	Yes	TBD	38%	80%	93%	50%	
Operational	Norway	Onboarding	Yes	TBD	43%	90%	100%	67%	
Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding		TBD	22%	70%	71%	67%	
Deployment	Latvia	TBD		TBD	22%	65%	57%	83%	
Deployment	Lithuania	TBD		TBD	32%	70%	57%	100%	
Onboarding	Croatia	TBD		TBD	13%	45%	50%	33%	
Onboarding	Ireland	TBD		TBD	19%	65%	50%	100%	
Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD		TBD	12%	20%	21%	17%	
Onboarding	Hungary	TBD		TBD	25%	60%	50%	83%	
Onboarding	Malta	TBD		TBD	15%	50%	43%	67%	
Onboarding	Romania	TBD		TBD	9%	30%	21%	50%	
					33	82%	82%	83%	80%

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Annex II. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Onboarding

GDI Node Operational Readiness	Step Phase Type				Onboarding														
	Technical	Non Technical	Non Technical	Non Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical							
Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Vanguard Node	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes =1, Partially=0.5)	Onboarding Overall Progress	Onboarding Tech Progress	Onboarding NonTech Progress	1.1.1	1.1.2	1.1.3	1.1.4	1.2.1	1.2.2	1.3.1	1.5.1	1.6.1	1.7.1	
									API use cases considered, specifications drafted and implementation in progress	Have started to build national capacity (ELSI, data quality, technical infrastructure functions) for the deployment of the 1+MG node and to support data flow.	Have developed the 1+MG NMG or equivalent structure to contribute to the 1+MG Initiative.	Have developed a national genomic plan or similar that secures long-term funding that matches the target implementation level.	Decision on services and components utilised	Software development best practises identified and implemented at the node	Security mitigation, management, and reporting system being drafted.	Have deployed or made available the initial physical infrastructure for the evaluation of the current PoC, or an upgraded version incorporating other additional use cases.	Have deployed and validated an instance or PoC or an upgraded version incorporating additional use cases	Load of synthetic data, functionalities demonstrated in development environment	
Operational	Belgium	Deployment	Yes	TBD	32%	85%	86%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	
Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment		TBD	29%	70%	64%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	
Operational	Denmark	Onboarding		TBD	53%	90%	93%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	Estonia	Onboarding		TBD	35%	80%	93%	50%	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	Finland	Operational	Yes	TBD	47%	95%	100%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	France	Deployment		TBD	53%	95%	93%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	Germany	Onboarding		TBD	49%	90%	93%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	
Operational	Italy	Deployment		TBD	40%	90%	86%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	
Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	Yes	TBD	25%	70%	64%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	
Operational	Portugal	Deployment		TBD	50%	90%	100%	67%	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding		TBD	49%	95%	100%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	Spain	Deployment	Yes	nboardi	49%	100%	100%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	Sweden	Deployment	Yes	nboardi	51%	100%	100%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	Yes	TBD	38%	80%	93%	50%	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	
Operational	Norway	Onboarding	Yes	TBD	43%	90%	100%	67%	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding		TBD	22%	70%	71%	67%	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	
Deployment	Latvia	TBD		TBD	22%	65%	57%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	No	No	
Deployment	Lithuania	TBD		TBD	32%	70%	57%	100%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	No	
Onboarding	Croatia	TBD		TBD	13%	45%	50%	33%	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Partially	
Onboarding	Ireland	TBD		TBD	19%	65%	50%	100%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	
Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD		TBD	12%	20%	21%	17%	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	Partially	Partially	No	No	
Onboarding	Hungary	TBD		TBD	25%	60%	50%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	
Onboarding	Malta	TBD		TBD	15%	50%	43%	67%	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	No	Yes	Partially	Partially	
Onboarding	Romania	TBD		TBD	9%	30%	21%	50%	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	Partially	Partially	No	
					33	82%	82%	83%	80%										
overall yes					63%	71%	68%	25%	67%	58%	54%	75%	42%	58%					
overall no					4%	4%	4%	21%	4%	17%	13%	4%	8%	25%					
overall partial					33%	25%	8%	54%	29%	33%	21%	50%	17%						
total completion					79%	83%	92%	52%	81%	71%	71%	85%	67%	67%					
Oper yes					80%	87%	93%	27%	80%	93%	80%	93%	60%	93%					
Oper no					0%	0%	0%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	7%						
Oper partial					20%	13%	7%	53%	20%	7%	20%	7%	40%	0%					
oper completion					90%	93%	97%	53%	90%	97%	90%	97%	80%	93%					

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Annex III. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Deployment

GDI Node Operational Readiness	Step Phase							2.1.1	2.1.2	2.2.1	2.2.2	2.3.1	2.3.2	2.4.1	2.4.2	2.5.1	2.6.1	2.7.1	2.8.1	2.9.1
	Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Vanguard Node	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes =1, Partially =0.5)	Deployment Tech Progress	Deployment Non Tech Progress	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment
									Non Technical	Non Technical	Technical	Non Technical	Non Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical
								Storage and network capacity needs achieved ad hoc by hosting institution	Common software development best practices employed	Minimal set of APIs for the five functionalities	Have built national capacity (ELSI, data quality, data standards, technical infrastructure functions) for the deployment of the 1+MG node and to support data flow	Network and storage meets reliability, robustness, performance, security, and capacity requirements	Deployment of 1+MG national node for connection to the staging environment with synthetic data loaded	Compliance and stress tests drafted and refined in context of requirements	Implementation & successful performance of compliance and stress tests of node in isolation	Have completed the initial data load of synthetic data and linking to staging version of 1+MG European Infrastructure	Deployment of 1+MG national node but it is not yet connected to the 1+MG Infrastructure	Communication established with user portal and 1+MG Infrastructure	Have finalised the initial deployment of national 1+MG production node enabling data access across borders in a staging environment	Production version ready to be deployed into production within the wider GDI
Operational	Belgium	Deployment	Yes	TBD	32%	6%	50%	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment		TBD	29%	6%	63%	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No						
Operational	Denmark	Onboarding		TBD	53%	22%	75%	Partially	Yes	No	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	No	No	No
Operational	Estonia	Onboarding		TBD	35%	17%	63%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No
Operational	Finland	Operational	Yes	TBD	47%	39%	75%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	Yes	No	No	No
Operational	France	Deployment		TBD	53%	33%	100%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially		Partially			
Operational	Germany	Onboarding		TBD	49%	44%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially		Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	
Operational	Italy	Deployment		TBD	40%	17%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	No
Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	Yes	TBD	25%	11%	13%	Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Partially	No	No
Operational	Portugal	Deployment		TBD	50%	56%	75%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	No	No
Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding		TBD	49%	44%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Yes	Partially	No	No
Operational	Spain	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	49%	39%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No
Operational	Sweden	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	51%	44%	88%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No
Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	Yes	TBD	38%	22%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
Operational	Norway	Onboarding	Yes	TBD	43%	44%	38%	Partially	Partially	Yes	No	Partially	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No
Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding		TBD	22%	0%	13%	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Deployment	Latvia	TBD		TBD	22%	0%	25%	Partially	No	No	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Deployment	Lithuania	TBD		TBD	32%	17%	63%	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No
Onboarding	Croatia	TBD		TBD	13%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Onboarding	Ireland	TBD		TBD	19%	0%	0%							No						
Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD		TBD	12%	0%	50%				Partially	Partially		No						
Onboarding	Hungary	TBD		TBD	25%	6%	50%	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Onboarding	Malta	TBD		TBD	15%	0%	0%							No						
Onboarding	Romania	TBD		TBD	9%	0%	0%													
					33.82%	23%	56%													
	overall yes				50%	46%	17%	4%	13%	25%	0%	0%	4%	8%	8%	8%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	overall no				17%	29%	33%	33%	29%	58%	46%	88%	67%	63%	67%	92%	100%			
	overall partial				33%	25%	50%	63%	58%	17%	54%	13%	29%	29%	25%	8%	0%			
	total completion				67%	58%	42%	35%	42%	33%	27%	6%	19%	23%	21%	4%	0%			
	Oper yes				73%	73%	27%	7%	20%	40%	0%	0%	7%	13%	13%	0%	0%			
	Oper no				0%	7%	7%	13%	13%	40%	20%	80%	47%	40%	47%	87%	100%			
	Oper partial				27%	20%	67%	80%	67%	20%	80%	20%	47%	47%	40%	13%	0%			
	oper completion				87%	83%	60%	47%	53%	50%	40%	10%	30%	37%	33%	7%	0%			

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Annex IV. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Operational

GDI Node Operational Readiness	Step Phase Type																	
	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	3.1.1	3.2.1	3.3.1	3.4.1	3.5.1	3.6.1	3.7.1	3.8.1	3.9.1	3.?.?	3.?.?			
Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Vanguard Node	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes = 1, Partially = 0.5)	Operational Tech Progress	Operational Non Tech Progress	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Non Technical	Non Technical		
								Periodic review of security of existing infrastructure to make sure it complies with current best practice	APIs assessed against users needs and feedback, updates scheduled	Periodic auditing and revision of network and storage capacity to ensure stakeholders needs are met	Compliance and stress tests regularly reviewed to ensure correspond to updated requirements and use cases	Deployment of national 1+MG Infrastructure node (production) enabling data access across borders when agreement allowing it are in place	Continuous support to Node interoperability, development, and security	Continuous 1+MG infrastructure developments to meet use cases needs	Evaluate and support technical solutions tested and and proposed by pillar III based on explicit use cases requirements	Node meets technical KPIs	Continuous Capacity building at European level	Continuous support to EU users via node helpdesk (ESI, data quality, data standards, technical infrastructure functions)
Operational	Belgium	Deployment	Yes	TBD	32%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment		TBD	29%	0%	0%											
Operational	Denmark	Onboarding		TBD	53%	39%	25%	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	Partially		
Operational	Estonia	Onboarding		TBD	35%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Operational	Finland	Operational	Yes	TBD	47%	0%	0%											
Operational	France	Deployment		TBD	53%	11%	25%	Partially		Partially						Partially		
Operational	Germany	Onboarding		TBD	49%	6%	0%	Partially										
Operational	Italy	Deployment		TBD	40%	0%	0%											
Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	Yes	TBD	25%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Operational	Portugal	Deployment		TBD	50%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding		TBD	49%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Operational	Spain	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	49%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Operational	Sweden	Deployment	Yes	nboardin	51%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	Yes	TBD	38%	0%	0%											
Operational	Norway	Onboarding	Yes	TBD	43%	0%	0%											
Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding		TBD	22%	0%	0%											
Deployment	Latvia	TBD		TBD	22%	0%	0%											
Deployment	Lithuania	TBD		TBD	32%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Onboarding	Croatia	TBD		TBD	13%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Onboarding	Ireland	TBD		TBD	19%	0%	0%											
Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD		TBD	12%	0%	0%											
Onboarding	Hungary	TBD		TBD	25%	0%	0%											
Onboarding	Malta	TBD		TBD	15%	0%	0%											
Onboarding	Romania	TBD		TBD	9%	0%	0%											
					33.82%	3%	3%											
					overall yes	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
					overall no	88%	96%	92%	96%	96%	96%	96%	100%	100%	100%	100%	92%	
					overall partial	8%	4%	8%	4%	4%	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	8%		
					total completion	8%	2%	4%	2%	2%	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4%	

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Annex V. Timelines for implementation according to target phase as

Onboarding: Croatia, Cyprus, Hungary, Ireland, Malta, Romania <i>Addressing national challenges for deployment</i>	Support
Involvement in 1+MG initiative (2024-Q4): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MS representatives participate in 1+MG MS meetings and Pillar I (GDI) - National experts are named and participate on the 1+MG WGs meetings (National implementation, ELIS, Sequencing, Standards, Infrastructure, Healthcare implementation, Health economics, Rare Diseases, Cancer, Common and complex (icl. Population genomics and Pharmacogenomics, infectious diseases) 	EC & Project coordination
Establishment of National Mirror groups (2025-Q2) National mirror group is in place (replicating 1+MG WG structure) and have regular meeting (e.g quarterly) to drive national implementation and adoption of 1+MG Roadmap and 1+MG Framework	EC & Project coordination
National genomic plan or equivalent (2026-Q4) Secure multi year funding to support the national operations of the 1+MG infrastructure (=> Workshop being planned for 24/4/2024 registration to be open)	EC & Project coordination
Deployment of GDI products in test environment (2025-Q4) Deployment of synthetic data and starter kit products on test environment (first release on 2023-Q3) and connected to test services (e.g. Test Beacon Network)	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination

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Deployment (in addition to Onboarding): Bulgaria, Latvia, Lithuania <i>Operational at the national level, not connected to EU operations</i>	Support
Deployment of GDI products in test environment (2024-Q4) Deployment of synthetic data and starter kit products on test environment (first release on <u>2023-Q3</u>) and connected to test services (e.g. Test Beacon Network)	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
Deployment of GDI products or interoperable solutions in pre-production environment (2025-Q3) Decision has been made on products that would be part of the national node and they are deployed in pre-production environment to join countries that has implemented Milestone 7 Data access governance demonstrator	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
National GDI node up up running in production environment providing services to the national community (2026-Q2) Deployment node realised	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination

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Operations (in addition to Deployment): Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands, Norway <i>Fully deployed national node Interconnected to EU services, able to provide access to data across borders following 1+MG Governance</i>	Support
Deployment of GDI products in test environment (2024-Q2) Deployment of synthetic data and starter kit products on test environment (first release on <u>2023-Q3</u>)	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
Deployment of GDI products or interoperable solutions in pre-production environment (2024-Q4) Decision has been made on products that would be part of the national node and they are deployed in pre-production environment to join countries that has implemented Milestone 7 Data access governance demonstrator	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
National GDI node up up running in production environment providing services to the national community (2025-Q3) Deployment node realised	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
National GDI node connected to EU level services and providing across border access (2026-Q2) Operational node realised	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination

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Annex VI. Visual progress of the Node Advancement

Technical Indicators.

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Node Goal & Level			Technical progress														
Readiness			Onboarding					Deployment					Operational				
Node	Target	Current Level	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%
Belgium	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Czech Republic	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Denmark	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Estonia	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Finland	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
France	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Germany	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Italy	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Luxembourg	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Portugal	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Slovenia	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Spain	Operational	Onboarding	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Sweden	Operational	Onboarding	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
The Netherlands	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Norway	Operational	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Bulgaria	Deployment	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Latvia	Deployment	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Lithuania	Deployment	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Croatia	Onboarding	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Ireland	Onboarding	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Cyprus	Onboarding	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Hungary	Onboarding	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Malta	Onboarding	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				
Romania	Onboarding	TBD	[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]					[Progress bars]				

Non-Technical Indicators

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M27-Q8			Non-Technical progress														
Node Goal & Level			Onboarding					Deployment					Operational				
Readiness			1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%
Node	Target	Current Level															
Belgium	Operational	TBD															
Czech Republic	Operational	TBD															
Denmark	Operational	TBD															
Estonia	Operational	TBD															
Finland	Operational	TBD															
France	Operational	TBD															
Germany	Operational	TBD															
Italy	Operational	TBD															
Luxembourg	Operational	TBD															
Portugal	Operational	TBD															
Slovenia	Operational	TBD															
Spain	Operational	Onboarding															
Sweden	Operational	Onboarding															
The Netherlands	Operational	TBD															
Norway	Operational	TBD															
Bulgaria	Deployment	TBD															
Latvia	Deployment	TBD															
Lithuania	Deployment	TBD															
Croatia	Onboarding	TBD															
Ireland	Onboarding	TBD															
Cyprus	Onboarding	TBD															
Hungary	Onboarding	TBD															
Malta	Onboarding	TBD															
Romania	Onboarding	TBD															

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